

KICHIK BIZNES VA TADBIRKORLIKNI RIVOJLANTIRISHDA INNOVASION MARKETINGDAN SAMARALI FOYDALANISH

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Annotasiya: Maqolada kichik biznes va tadbirkorlikning samarali vositasi hamda asosi bo'lib marketing hisoblanadi. Marketing imkoniyatlari keng va doimiyliigi, uni o'rganish biznesda muvaffaqiyatga erishishning asosiy dastagi ekanligi yoritilgan.

Kalitli so'zlar: kichik biznes, tadbirkorlik, marketing, innovatsion mahsulot, bozorni o'rganish, potensial xaridor, tovar kategoriyasi, korxonaning raqobatbardoshligi, innovatsion marketing, biznesni rivojlantirish.

Аннотация: В статье говорится, что маркетинг является эффективным инструментом и основой малого бизнеса и предпринимательства. Широкий и постоянный охват маркетинговых возможностей освещается тем фактом, что его изучение является основным рычагом для достижения успеха в бизнесе.

Ключевые слова: малый бизнес, предпринимательство, маркетинг, инновационный продукт, исследование рынка, потенциальный покупатель, товарная категория, конкурентоспособность предприятия, инновационный маркетинг, развитие бизнеса.

Annotation: The article is marketing as an effective tool and foundation of small business and entrepreneurship. Marketing opportunities are broad and continuous, its study is lit up that it is the mainstay of success in business.

Keywords: small business, entrepreneurship, marketing, innovative product, market study, potential buyer, brand category, competitiveness of the enterprise, innovative marketing, business development.

Marketing - iste'molchilar muammolarini anglash va bozor faoliyatini tartibga solishga aniq maksadga yo'naltirilgan jarayon hisoblanadi. Marketing (inglizchadan market - bozor) - bu mahsulotni ishlab chiqarishdan boshlab toki uni sotishni tashkil etilishigacha bo'lgan majmuaviy tizimdir. U aniq haridorlarni talabini qondirish, bozorni o'rganish va oldindan ko'ra bilish asosida foyda olishga mo'ljallangan.

Turli xil mulk shaklidagi kichik biznes korxonalari ishlab chiqarish, sotish faoliyati marketing rejasi bilan o'zaro yaqindan bog'langan bo'lishi kerak. Marketing konsepsiyasi bozorda kichik biznes korxonasining umumiy yutuqlarini ta'minlash nuqtai nazaridan uning faoliyatining barcha sohalarida qarorlar qabul qilishini ko'zda tutadi. Bu holat tashkiliy, boshqaruv va sotish ishlarining har xil turlarida o'z aksini topishi kerak.

Kichik biznesdagi xo‘jalik yurituvchi subyektlar har doim aniq haridorni mo‘ljallab qilib quyidagi savollarga javob topishlari kerak: Qancha? Qay darajada sifatli? Nimadan? Qachon mahsulot ishlab chiqarilishi kerak? Bundan ma‘lumki kichik tadbirkorlik tarkiblari soni, sifati va vaqt o‘lchamlari bo‘yicha cheklanganligidan kelib chiqadi. Ular bozorni egallash uchun amalga oshirayotgan xo‘jalik operatsiyalarining harajatlarini haridorlar uchun olib boriladigan raqobat kurashida yutib chiqish uchun kamaytirib borishlari zarur. Natijada potensial haridor uning taklif etgan tovarini harid qiladi. Bu muammoni yechishda marketing muhim dastak hisoblanadi. Marketing yangiliklari tadbirkorlik faoliyatini rivojlantirishda muhim rol o‘ynaydi. Innovatsion mahsulot yoki tovar kategoriyasi bozoriga kirish biznesni yanada muvaffaqiyatli qilish imkonini beradi. Tadqiqotlarni amalga oshirishning zamonaviy usullarini qo‘llash, mijozlarni jalb qilish yangi mijozlarning o‘shirishini ta‘minlaydi, korxonaning raqobatbardoshligini oshiradi.

Biznesni rivojlantirish har doim savdo aylanishining oshishi, assortimentning kengayishi bilan birga keladi. Buni yangi mahsulot yoki xizmatlarni vakolatli rivojlantirmasdan amalga oshirish mumkin emas. Bozor yangiliklarini taqdim qilmasdan va maqsadli auditoriyani jalb qilish tizimini takomillashtirmasdan, raqobatchilar doimo oldinga siljiydi, har qanday reytingda birinchi o‘rinni egallash uchun eng yangi mahsulotlarni ishlab chiqadi va ko‘proq xaridorlar va iste‘molchilarni jalb qilish uchun daromadni kamaytirishi mumkin. xizmatlar.

Innovatsion marketing nafaqat mahsulot o‘zgarishini, balki ularga maqsadli auditoriyani jalb qilish usullarini ham anglatadi. U talabni shakllantiradi, uning asosiy vazifasi hozirgi va kelajakdagi mijozlarning istaklari va ehtiyojlarini qondirishdir.

Marketing yangiliklari -bu faoliyatning bilimlarini joriy etish yoki birlashtirish, eng yangi mahsulot va xizmatlarni joriy etish bilan bevosita bog‘liq bo‘lgan jarayonlarning to‘plamidir. Marketing yangiliklari orqali korxonaning raqobatbardoshligini oshirish amalga oshiriladi. Marketing va innovatsion faoliyatni bir-biri bilan bog‘lash marketing innovatsiyalari kontseptsiyasini o‘z ichiga oladi, uning maqsadi iste‘molchilarning kam qondirilgan yoki yashirin so‘rovlarini aniqlash, bozorda yangi mahsulotlarni ishlab chiqish va targ‘ib qilish, bu talablarni qondirishdir.

Innovatsiyalar marketingi O‘zbekistonda innovatsion faoliyatning rivojlantirilishi lozim bo‘lgan sohalaridan biridir. Ma‘lumki, rejali iqtisodiyot sharoitlarida mahsulot iste‘molchilari to‘g‘risida qarorlar markazlashtirilgan tarzda qabul qilinib, ishlab chiqaruvchilarga yangi o‘zlashtirilayotgan mahsulot turlari sotuvi strategiyasi to‘g‘risida o‘ylashga zarurat mavjud emasdi. Bozor islohotlarining 2-3 yillarida iste‘mol bozorining katta hajmi korxonalar rahbarlarining marketing sohasida loqaydligini keltirib chiqargan edi. Biroq, davlat dasturlar tizimi va innovatsion korxonalarining zaruriy moddiy-texnik va moliyaviy resurslar bilan ta‘minlanishi

tegishli markazlashtirilgan tarzda amalga oshirish bo'lmaganligi, ko'pchilik innovasion korxonalarini maxsus ishlab chiqarishni qisqartirib, ommaviy iste'mol uchun texnologik liniyalar sotib olishga majbur qildi. Bu kabi qarorlarning asosiy qismi faoliyatini saqlab qolish va turli yo'llar bilan ishlab chiqarish jamoalari shtat jadvalini qisqartirmaslik yuzasidan qabul qilinadi.

Hozirgi kunda innovasion korxonalar oldida ishlab chiqarish texnologik bazasini yangilash, ishlab chiqariladigan mahsulot sifatini oshirish, Sotuv bozorlarini kengaytirish, shuningdek, eksport salohiyatini oshirish kabi dolzarb vazifalar turibdi. Ushbu vazifalarni samarali hal etish faol innovasion siyosat yuritish va innovasion korxonada marketing faoliyatini rivojlantirishni talab etadi.

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